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A Comparative Analysis of The Nation, Daily Sun, Thisday and Daily Trust Newspapers Framing of 2023 Presidential Election

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Abstract

The study was carried out to examine how four Nigerian national newspapers (The Nation, Daily Sun, This Day and Daily Trust) framed the 2023 presidential election. Using the content analysis, data were sourced from 235 editorial contents of the four newspapers published between August 2022 and July 2023, which yielded a population of 365 editions. The systematic sampling procedure guided the determination of the sample size, while the defined skip interval was applied in the actual selection of the sample size at 25% of the population, which yielded 91.2 editions. A quantitative and qualitative descriptive analysis was adopted while data were reported as the mean and simple percentage of the group total. Findings revealed the use of dominant frames such as issue-based, personality-based, conflict, news and strategic as well as ethnic/religious frames. It was also discovered that ownership and political affiliations obviously influenced the framing of the 2023 presidential election to the extent that The Nation and Daily Sun newspapers published 95% and 92% stories in favour of the All Progressive Congress (APC) respectively, while this Day and Daily Trust demonstrated moderate objectivity through the even spread of stories across the political parties. The study calls for more responsible journalism, urging media outlets to prioritize issue-based reporting and factual analysis over partisan and sensational coverage.

Keywords: Framing, direction, party affiliation, ownership, public sphere

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Introduction

The framing of political events by media organizations plays a crucial role in shaping public opinion perceptions. In the context of Nigeria's 2023 presidential election, a comparative analysis of the editorial content and reportage by *The Nation*, *Daily Sun*, *ThisDay* and *Daily Trust* newspapers reveals how factors such as ownership, operational base and party affiliation influenced media framing.

The framing of political events by media organizations plays a crucial role in shaping public opinion, and this in turn influences how one relates to others and to other events, including politics and voting decisions (Adamu, Balogun & Ofem, 2024). According to Ogbodo, Igbo & Duru (2021), framing is understood to mean the journalistic approach of including some aspects of an event in reporting it while leaving out others. However, professionalism in journalism stipulates strict adherence to the principles of fairness, balance and objectivity in news reporting, but the principle of objectivity can be compromised in various ways, including political bias, corporate influence, sensationalism, conflict of interest, government censorship and propaganda (Omula & Emmanuel, 2024). Supporting the compromise of objectivity, Ojomo (2017) and Abramowicz (2024) included misuse of anonymous sources, framing, selective reporting, social media influence, misinformation, cultural and ideological bias, omission and underreporting.

In the context of Nigeria's 2023 presidential election, the explorations of this study periscopes a comparative analysis of the framing of editorial content and reportage by *The Nation*, *Daily Sun*, *This Day* and *Daily Trust* newspapers, and how such factors as ownership, operational base and party affiliation influenced media framing.

There are scholarly submissions that ownership and political leanings often dictate editorial slant, with media organizations aligning their narratives with the interests of their proprietors or associated political figures (Ojomo, 2017; Omula & Emmanuel, 2024). For insurance, The Nation newspaper, owned by Ahmed Bola Tinubu, is widely perceived as sympathetic to the All Progressive Congress (APC). Daily Sun historically aligned with the Peoples Democratic Party (PDP) but recently *romancing* with the APC due to the defection of its owner, Orji Uzor Kalu, to the All Progressive Congress (APC), believed to be influenced by its ownership structure and editorial tradition. *ThisDay*, owned by Nduka Obiagbena, who is also the editor-in-

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chief, is known for its elite-driven focus, often reflecting the perspectives of influential stakeholders, while Daily Trust newspaper, with its operational base in northern Nigeria, provides a unique regional lens that influences its framing of national events.

This study explores how these factors shaped the portrayal of candidates, party policies, and electoral processes before, during, and after the 2023 presidential election by examining headline trends, editorial priorities, and thematic coverage. The analysis highlights the interplay between media ownership, regional dynamics, and political affiliations in framing the narratives that informed and influenced public discourse during the period of study.

Statement of the Problem

How the framing of news and other editorial content in the studied newspapers reflected the influence of ownership, party affiliation and operational base is not a novel study, but the nexus between the 2023 Nigerian presidential election and reportage by *The Nation*, *Daily Sun*, *ThisDay* and *Daily Trust* newspapers and a good mix of ownership provided a unique case study. Previous studies include but are not limited to Okocha & Gupta (2018) "Influence of media owners' political affiliations on journalistic professionalism in Ghana"; Mordi & Ogbu (2017) "The influence of newspaper ownership on the objectivity of the coverage of Nigeria's 2015 presidential election"; and Okwuchukwu (2014) "The influence of media ownership and control on media agenda setting in Nigeria". Although commercialization can also play a crucial role in framing, this study critically examined the framing of news and editorial content of the 2023 presidential election by *The Nation*, *Daily Sun*, *ThisDay* and *Daily Trust* newspapers to establish the adherence to professionalism. In other words, which of the studied newspapers reflected more propensity to party affiliation, ownership and regional influence in negation to professionalism, as evidenced by the volume of framing?

Objectives of the study

The study set out to comparatively:

1. Examine the frames used by *The Nation*, *Daily Sun*, *ThisDay* and *Daily Trust* newspapers in the coverage of the 2023 presidential election.
2. Ascertain the direction of stories on the 2023 presidential election by the studied newspapers.

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3. Examine how the framing of news and editorial contents reflected the influence of ownership, party affiliation and operational-base by the studied newspapers.

Newspaper and Politics in Nigeria

It would be preposterous to imagine the existence of democracy in Nigeria without acknowledging the contributions of the press towards its success. This fact is obviated by the very nature of democracy as dependent on popular will, which is predicated upon popular opinion, public awareness and knowledge. Indeed, the mass media for the consolidation of democracy. This constitutes the cardinal responsibility of the press: to gather and process factual, unbiased reports which are eventually disseminated to the public as the news of the day, including interpretations of the complexities and analysis of the news. By so doing, newspapers succeed in playing a crucial role in the political development of Nigeria.

A vibrant press can only thrive where there is press freedom, and freedom of the press is best guaranteed under liberal democracy. It is the mass media and the press in particular that provide the awareness which serves as a check and balance against the abuse of power by the government of the day. They also define their communities by providing information about daily and weekly occurrences (Folkerts & Lacey, 2005; Su and Borah, 2021).

The press and politics are functionally inseparable because politics permeates every facet of society. It is an aspect of the society that virtually determines how lives should be lived (Nwabueze, 2009; Komlik & Komlik, 2021). Politics is the 'loom' that holds the society together, and no nation can survive without political control. Accordingly, whenever there is a political vacuum, there is a tendency for anarchy to set in.

Politics includes the sum total of activities which are directly or indirectly linked to the capture, consolidation and deployment of state power machinery and is not restricted to actions of rulers, even as there are also invisible de facto hands in government (Przeworski, 2019). Oyedele (2022), in his "Issue-based politics and economic development in Nigeria", agrees that politics is the process of choosing public leaders that manage the affairs of a geopolitical entity, especially the security and economy of nations, through periodic elections.

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Interestingly, the press should function for the oneness of the federation; they should also ensure that the polity is not needlessly inflamed but rather actively maintained for the stability of the society. To ensure a responsible press, Uche (1989) warns against allowing “excited reseals” at the control of the mass media because there is a need for the regulation of ownership.

Coincidentally, the history of the Nigerian press is tied to the political evolution of the diverse ethnic, cultural and social segments that metamorphosed into present-day Nigeria. It was the press that championed the cause for independence from the apron strings of colonialism, and a cursory look into the past reveals a stunning secret: those who emerged as the leaders of the newly independent Nigeria were the major actors of pre-colonial newspapering. And shortly after six years of parliamentary democracy came the nightmarish interlude of thirteen years of military rule in the Nigerian political scene, a period that witnessed a series of abuses of press freedom (Napoli, 2019).

Of course, the military wouldn't have appeared in the scene without the massive rigging of elections in the western part of Nigeria, a situation that deteriorated into political rioting, arson, killings and lootings (Feaver, 2022). It therefore becomes necessary to observe that the press, in the coverage of this political impasse, was accused of bias and inflammatory comments that heated up the polity to the proportion of anarchy, a situation which prompted the military to promulgate Decrees No. 2 and No. 4.

However, despite the draconian Decrees No. 2 and No. 4, which protected corrupt military officials from being exposed to public debate for transparency and accountability, the Nigerian press lived up to public expectations, and their doggedness in whipping up public support which led the military to bow out in 1979. Adesoji (2019) castigated “the political influence of the Nigerian press from 1967 to 1979 when the Northern military and political leaders and their Yoruba counterparts banded together in a conspiratory unity to share the economic, political and military war booties after the defeat of the Igbos. Uche may not have been totally correct in his observation here because the newspapers owned by prominent Igbos were also guilty of parochialism and tribalism in their direction and frames (Adesoji, 2019; Ojo, 2020).

Both the second and third republics witnessed active involvement of the press in politics, but the advent of the social media platforms made the 2023 presidential election uniquely exceptional. It is instructive to recall that a similar scenario played out in the 2015 presidential election in Nigeria, where Muhammadu Buhari crested into power

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through his popularity on social media, but, on a sad undertone, his administration severely attempted to ban social media. This ignoble attempt ended in futility, proving that social media have come to stay and cannot be gagged by despotic regimes.

Thus, in a bid to stem the influence of social media, newspapers also introduced their own versions of social media platforms, combining the advantageous characteristics of broadcast and interactive media digitization. In relation to the major objectives of this study, newspapers or the press and politics in Nigeria are functional partners whose relationship is predicated upon several factors, among which are ownership, the government of the day and the several laws that regulate the operations of the press.

Media Framing as an Influence on Cognitive Bias

Collectively, the mass media perform a crucial role during the process of election, and print media, as the pioneer of the mass media, is pivotal in framing issues, promoting candidates and granting candidates and other political actors a platform for political discussions. Studies on election campaign coverage have found that the media tend to emphasize two news frames traditionally linked to politics (Ecker, Lewandowsky & Chadwick, 2020; Bode & Vraga, 2021; Tewksbury & Rittenberg, 2021), and these two news frames include strategic game frame and issues framing. The implication here is that both current and emerging issues could be strategically framed or presented in news stories depending on how they were deliberated upon by journalists or the editorial board for specific impact on the psyche of the audience members (Obukoadata & Enam, 2016; Usher, 2021).

Writing further on the strategic game frame, Muniz, Saldierna & Mararion (2018) explained a game where politics and the electoral process are put forward separately and as a set of interactive and related messages spatially and temporarily bound together (Arowolo, 2017; Ruiz & Barnett, 2021), while the news frame involves different political tactics developed by candidates, political parties, rulers and a willing press to improve their chances of triumph (Adeyemi, 2020).

The bottom line is that framing is specifically applied in news stories and may be unobtrusively or consciously done. Other editorial content, such as features, articles, and editorials, among others, are considered either individual or institutional opinions, whereas news stories are expected to be objective, balanced, and unbiased accounts of

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timely occurrences. Hence, Tversky & Kahneman (2003) in Obukoadata & Enam (2016) confirm that the media frames give the audience aspects of issues to think about, and it is left for the audience to form their perception based on how they can relate their understanding with other information they could access.

Like agenda setting, which, of course, is linked to framing, it focuses on aspects of issues that are relevant but differs from agenda setting by emphasizing the essence of certain aspects of an issue rather than the entire picture. Put differently, bits and pieces of related events, themes and issues are structured and organized into frames by the media and presented to the audience members as information with the hidden intention of shaping their perceptions and cognition (Arowolo, 2017). Newspaper framing is guided by the principle that rhetorical devices can be used in a strategic arrangement to convince audience members of the salience of any given position. This submission aligns with the postulations of Arowolo (2017) that as a second level of agenda setting, framing examines the relative salience of attributes of issues with public issues providing the information content. It is generally difficult to define the scope of issues that come under the public purview, but certainly political and election matters, including campaigns, policy, and issues bordering on conflict, merit attention (Ceron & Memoli, 2020; Benkler, Faris, & Roberts, 2023; Strömbäck & Esser, 2024).

Scholarly explorations on media framing abound. Oriola, Omotayo & Ajayi (2022) point out that “the characteristic manner of news by political journalists called framing could result in certain directions of perception in the public and lead to voting action”. Muniz, Salderina and Maranon (2018) had earlier aligned with this strategy of promoting a particular framing to present issues and candidates, which also grants citizens access into political debate, thereby making them active participants in the electioneering process.

The general assumption that the coverage of elections is different from everyday political coverage is debatable, and the argument is that such a distinction is factored in by the nature of political institutions and also relative to the political culture and environment in question (McMenamin, Courtney & McNutty, 2021). For instance, in the stable and developed democratic western nations where there are established political institutions, the trend is that an election is capable of choosing a government, while the reverse is true in developing countries with weak institutions. In such consensual countries like Nigeria and other third world countries, election coverage usually moves

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away from political competition and policy towards policy negotiations and negative framing. However, whether negative or positive, McNemanim *et al.* (2021) demonstrate the yardstick for determining the nature of framing to include the proportion of space, the ratio of soft to hard news, episodic stories versus general thematic frames and, of course, the tone of the news as well as the distribution of the stories among the political parties and candidates. Aalberg, Strömbäck & de Vreese (2012) confirm that media coverage of elections in Europe and North America has increasingly focused on campaigns as a game rather than policy debate, hinting that the high standard of living in the Western democracies is responsible for less pressure on the media.

However, Dimitrova & Stromback (2012) declared a glaring lack of empirical studies to evaluate the pattern of news frames used between different electoral processes from a longitudinal content analysis perspective. This approach may not be the focus of this study, but its adoption has contributed to valuable theoretical perspectives.

Documenting the study of election campaigns by different media must recognize the nature of campaign which is usually in three phases:

Furthermore, investigations that use different political news frames in the course of the electoral process are limited, especially because election campaigns are not static – they tend to vary in coverage and intensity of informational treatment offered to proposals, candidates, etc. Usually, election had been divided into three stages or phases that define the course of the election campaign. Positive approaches usually dominate the first stage or initial phase, where the presentation of the candidate dominates. The second or intermediate stage is usually dominated by strategies of programmatic presentation and government proposals presented by the candidates... A negative campaign with attacks between candidates is also present at this state. Finally, the third stage or phase is the most crucial for candidates; in this phase, horse race presentation and strategic game frame tend to be emphasized through polarization between candidates and their strategies to obtain victory and win the election (Freidenberg & Gouzalez, 2009; Muniz, Saldierna & Maranon, 2008).

Media framing is goal-directed in consonance with every purposeful communication event. This explains why isolated bits of issues are usually emphasized in order to influence cognitive bias. Boyce (2021) identifies about four types of media frames, including the visual frame, which uses colour, font size and imagery to contextualize a topic; the auditory frame; the value frame; and positive and negative

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frames. This study examined the application of frames to news stories on the 2023 presidential election by *The Nation*, *Daily Sun*, *ThisDay* and *Daily Trust* newspapers and how they manifested in headlines, themes and frequencies, as well as the framing of issues related to the election.

Citizen Journalism and the Coverage of Election

In the face of heavy censorship and the government's control of the mainstream media, citizen journalism provides safety for the masses to liberate their feelings and gain unadulterated information on politics and other topical issues. This is journalism conducted by non-professionals who disseminate information using websites, blogs and social media platforms, and it has miraculously expanded its worldwide influence despite professional concerns. Interestingly, citizen journalism has come to play a significant role in twenty-first-century political events, allowing every member of the society equal opportunity to gather and share information as news to the public. Citizen journalism dissolves the thin veneer between the audience and the media and, in fact, transforms the audience to the dual capacity of source and audience, placing professional journalists under pressure. Pekin (2003) in Isah, Abdulazeez, Kadiri & Asemah (2023) confirm that citizen journalism is an expression of people's belief in the dispensability of professional journalists and attestation of their ability to sort out themselves in contingencies. They demonstrated citizen journalism, as mud raking – limited or total absence of ethical and professional restraints – results in the digging of information behind the surface, which sometimes goes contrary to ethical values. Again, the monotonous litany of governments hypocrisy with such euphemisms as “under the context of law and order”, “the oneness of *the nation*” and “national unity” does not inhibit the practice of citizen journalism. Sometimes the disruption of the status quo and exposure of governments' cover-ups motivate its practice.

Here in Nigeria, citizen journalism is confronted with a plethora of challenges in “mud racking, including illiteracy, high cost of 'surfing' the net and a lack of electronic gadgets to access the social media platform, among others. Indeed, it was similar challenges that drove the traditional media into blogging and interactive media communication in the face of dwindling readership. Hence, citizen journalism is fast becoming an alternative platform for the common man to participate in the process of selecting leaders for democratic governance (Tsgyu, 2016; Okocha & Akpe, 2022).

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Although considered an unconventional mode of journalism, Sam Onwe (2022) points out that with just an internet-enabled camera phone, we can report and transmit our lived experiences of significant events in real time ahead of and outside of traditional media structures. As a form of participatory journalism with robust data and information, it complements traditional journalism.

There is a growing distrust among the citizens of the traditional media. A distrust that paved the way for citizen journalism to flourish, and no amount of the government's regulations can put a stop to citizen journalism. This does not imply that citizen journalism is totally bereft of advantages, as it played a crucial role in shaping perspective before, during, and after 2023 presidential election, although most of the information from social media cannot be verified, and this is a major cause for concern. Nevertheless, the advantages of citizen journalism outweigh its shortcomings. For instance, in the build-up to the 2015 presidential election, former president Muhammadu Buhari swept into Aso Rock, edging out the sitting president, Goodluck Jonathan, through the power of citizen journalism. Furthermore, several reforms have been made possible as a result of the articulation of citizen journalism.

It is debatable between the mainstream traditional journalism and citizen journalism which one sets the agenda for the other to follow, as most suppressed information is broken through citizen journalism, only for the mainstream media to respond with careful framing of such issues. Conversely, as earlier hinted, citizen journalism breaks the bounds set by traditional journalism, censorship and other regulations, expounding on issues which the mainstream media had framed into a narrow perspective. By so doing, citizen journalists generate emerging issues for topical discussion.

Empirical Studies

Study I: Gibbs, N. and Patterson T. (2024) "Media Framing of Elections in a Polarized Landscape", Harvard Kennedy School 2024

Procedure:

The researchers purposed to identify how the impacts of media narratives as well as their presentation affect public opinion and voting decisions, employing the explorations of traditional and social media to demonstrate how they contribute to echo chambers and ideological entrenchment. To achieve their goal, the authors focused on how changes in

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media ownership, funding models and digital algorithms affect the quality and diversity of political information, guided by the following objectives:

1. To examine how medial framing shapes electoral dynamics in polarized political environment.
2. To analyze the role of media platforms in reinforcing political divides.
3. To investigate economic and technological disruptions in journalism.

Findings

The study revealed that media framing actually amplifies polarization to the extent that media stations often emphasize aspects of issues and narratives that favour their policies and ownership structure, which sometimes fosters mistrust between opposing political groups. Such framings are also attributed to declining revenue in traditional journalism leading to 'click-driven' sensational content over substantive political reporting. Finally, the study discovered that polarized media coverage has eroded public confidence in both journalism and democratic institutions.

Recommendations

1. The researchers advocated for a balanced coverage of issues from across political spectrum.
2. Development of sustainable funding and business strategies that prioritize public service over profit.
3. Improvement of algorithm transparency to promote diverse view prints in users newsfeeds.

Study II: Adamu, Joy J., Balogun, Naeem A and Ofen, Kebesobase I. (2024)

“Newspaper Framing of Negeria's 2011-2015 Presidential Elections” Nasadrawa Journal of Multimedia and Communication Studies, Vol. 6(1), 128-137.

Owing to the controversy that surrounded Nigeria's 2011-2015 elections, Adama, Balogun & Ofem conducted a qualitative methodical content analysis on two carefully selected national dailies, viz.: *Daily Trust* and *The Punch* newspapers. The study covered a period of 30 days to 2011 and 2015 elections, which gave a total of 120 editions.

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Procedure

The study was anchored on framing theory and the propaganda model to unravel how the studied newspapers presented aspects of issues related to the 2011-2015 presidential election in a way that suggests a particular interpretation. Interestingly, this study is relevant to the current work by the researcher since it adopts both the content analysis research method and the framing theory.

Findings

1. The study identified noticeable differences in the reportage of *Daily Trust* and *The Punch* newspapers with regards to the type of frame, tone, frequency and prominence (the placement of the story on the front page, considering the font size and space allotted). In other words, findings revealed that *Daily Trust* which is a northern based paper is subtly pro-Buhari.
2. Findings further revealed that news filters showed elites' quotes (news sources) dominating to a large extent, especially in *The Punch*.

Study III: Obukoadata, P. O. and Enam, V. (2016).

“Reflective Images of Media Frames, Objectivity and Presentation of Boko Haram Insurgency in selected Newspapers” *AKSU Journal of Communication Research*, 1(1), 103-120.

The study was concerned with how selected newspapers coloured, labelled and framed news stories on Boko Haram. Three national dailies, including *The Punch*, *Vanguard* and *Daily Trust*, were selected to represent the northern and southern regions of Nigeria; while *The Punch* and *Vanguard* are based in the South, *Daily Trust* is based in Abuja. The researchers explored framing and agenda-setting theories in their bid to answer the following research questions:

1. What words are predominantly used to frame Boko Haram insurgency in the selected newspapers?
2. How objectively do the selected newspapers frame Boko Haram insurgency?
3. How does newspaper framing of Boko Haram influence editorial decision of other newspapers/media?

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The content analysis method of investigation was used in the study to analyze headlines and leads of stories as units of analysis over a period of one year. The study concluded by identifying a diatribe between the processes of media framing and agenda setting which ultimately abolishes any hold on the tenets of objectivity. The implication here is that while media agenda-setting starts from a point, media framing ultimately shapes public opinion on certain issues.

It is worthy of mention that both the theoretical framework and the methodology of the study are useful and consistent with this research work and therefore provide a ready resource for comparison. For instance, the front page, back page, inside front page, inside back page and inside page were chosen as pages of prominence. However, The *Punch* newspaper had the highest percent (45%) of Boko Haram stories, followed by *Daily Trust* newspaper (36.1%), which could be a result of it being a northern-based newspaper that tries to show some degree of respect. The *Vanguard* newspaper came last with few news contents concerning Boko Haram (121%).

Theoretical framework

Three theories relevant to this study are agenda setting, framing and the public sphere. Three theories relevant to this study are agenda setting, framing and the public sphere.

Agenda setting

The agenda-setting theory was propounded by the duo of Maxwell McCombs and Donald Shaw in their seminal 1972 study during the United States presidential election, and the rationale for this theory is its relationship with the contents of the media as being capable of setting an agenda for topical discussion and, by extension, the salience of the topic in the public mind. In other words, the agenda-setting hypothesis assumes a direct positive relationship between media coverage of issues (political, economic, societal, among others) and the amount of attention attached to such issues or a specific aspect of the topic that will set the agenda for public discussion (Folarin, 1998; Akakwandu, 2020).

Anaeto, Onabajo & Osifeso (2008) confirm that agenda-setting theory does not ascribe to the media the power to determine what we actually think, but it does ascribe to them the power to determine what we think about. Accordingly, when people are exposed to similar media content from a specific perspective, it is possible for the same group of people to place importance on similar issues.

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The theory is often divided into two levels, with the first level focusing on the salience of issues while the second level delves into framing – how the media presents and interprets issues to shape opinion – and the core assumptions of the theory include:

1. The media filters and shapes reality, determining which issues are presented and how.
2. Public attention tends to align with the issues the media prioritizes.
3. The media's ability to set the agenda is most influential during times of uncertainty or when audiences lack direct knowledge of the issues being reported (Soroka, 2002; McCombs, 2004).

Summarily, it is worthy to mention that agenda-setting theory highlights the significant role of the media in shaping public priorities and political discourse. While it remains highly influential, it is important to consider its limitations in a rapidly evolving media landscape, where audiences have greater access to diverse sources of information. Despite the evolving media landscape, this theory is useful to this study, as it provides a deep insight into how the studied newspapers presented their news and editorial contents during and after the 2023 presidential election in Nigeria.

Framing theory

The first documented academic exploration of the framing theory is linked to Gregory Bateson, who defined 'psychological frames' as a spatial and temporary bounding of a set of interactive messages (Bateson, 1972; Arowolo, 2017). The theory is linked to agenda setting, and its basis is that the media, while focusing on specific issues, events and objects, place them within a field of meaning, and this qualifies framing as a 'scheme of interpretation, a collection of anecdotes and stereotypes that individuals rely upon to understand and respond to events' (Arowolo, 2017; Akakwandu, 2020).

Framing theory explains the role of the media in presenting a 'frame' to the audience, an aspect of an issue capable of influencing people's choices of information processing and consumption. While agenda setting explains a composite picture of an issue, framing theory explains that the media create this frame by introducing news items with predefined narrow contextualization, with the sole aim of shaping the public opinion and perspectives to align with the frames (Arowolo, 2017; Nwaboli & Abiodun, 2003).

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As a process, framing involves a series of elements that interact to create reality. Some aspects of the general issue are selected and strategically presented for psychological effect, and such emphasis obviates the salience of the attributes of the general issue which had earlier set the agenda for topical discussion. Supporting this narrative, Akakwandu (2020) encapsulated that in practical terms, the theory explains how reporters, editors and other public affairs practitioners, through agenda-setting functions, surveillance and interpretation, highlight certain events and then place them within a particular context to encourage or discourage certain interpretations, perspectives and actions.

This theory is relevant to this study as a guiding framework for diagnosing how *The Nation*, *Daily Sun*, *ThisDay* and *Daily Trust* newspapers, through their news stories, features, editorials, cartoons and other editorial content, selected and emphasized attributes related to the broad issue of the 2023 presidential election in Nigeria.

Public Sphere Theory

Another model relevant to the framing of the 2023 presidential election by *The Nation*, *Daily Sun*, *ThisDay* and *Daily Trust* newspapers is the public sphere theory developed by Jurgen Habermas in his 1972 work 'The Structural Transformation of the Public Sphere'. Habermas describes the public sphere as a space where individuals come together to interact and freely discuss and debate societal issues. This sphere is characterized by rational-critical discourse, which fosters democratic participation by enabling citizens to form opinions and influence decision-making.

According to Habermas, the public sphere is a mediating space between the state and society, where individuals engage with the media to critically assess public policies, governance and political candidates. The role of the media in the public sphere is crucial, as it provides the information and platforms necessary for debate. However, Habermas warns that commercialization and vested interests in the media may distort this role, prioritizing sensationalism or elite interests over the public good (Folarin, 1998; McQuail, 2019).

Methodology

The researchers adopted content analysis as their method of investigation. The data for analysis were sourced from 235 editorial contents of four Nigerian national newspapers

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(*The Nation*, *Daily Sun*, *ThisDay* and *Daily Trust*), which reflected a good mix of ownership, in addition to an even geographical spread, and thus were relevant to the 2023 presidential election. Published between August 2022 and July 2023, the newspapers yielded a population of 365 editions, and the period of study was justified based on its ability to cover campaign and pre-election activities, election day and immediate impacts as well as post-election developments.

The systematic sampling procedure guided the determination of the sample size, while the defined skip interval was applied in the actual selection of the sample, estimated at 25% of the population, which yielded 91.2 editions. Units of analysis were straight news stories, headlines, editorials, themes, features, and cartoons contained in all the studied newspapers relating to the 2023 presidential election, using the Cohen's Kappa formula for the intercoder reliability test, Wimmer & Dominick (2020).

$$\text{i.e. Kappa} = \frac{\% \text{ observed} - \% \text{ expected}}{N \times M} = \% \text{ expected}$$

Coders were selected and subjected to pre-coding training. Two training sessions were conducted. The third session was the actual coding of 25% of the sample contents of the study. The coding sheet captured the page placement, weighting, tone and direction of stories on the 2023 presidential election as they involved major political parties, candidates, campaign strategies and policies. A quantitative and qualitative descriptive analysis was adopted while data were reported as the mean and simple percentage of the group total. However, the percentage determinations of the respective groups were presented graphically. Statistical analysis was performed using GraphPad Prism version 5.03 for Windows. A grouped bar chart was used to compare differences between selected newspapers in the same category of report, and one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used to test for variation in newspaper activity among selected groups. Post hoc comparison of means was performed by Bonferroni's multiple comparison, and $p < 0.05$ was considered to represent a statistically significant difference between test populations.

Data presentation

Figure 1: Size of Headlines used in 2023 Presidential Election story

In Figure 1, the 48.3 mean % of 1 deck/72 points indicates the front page treatment of 2023 presidential election news coverage by the four understudied newspapers. *The Nation* newspaper devoted 55.2% to 1 deck prominent headlines and 26.3% to double deck / 36-72 points; *Daily Sun* newspaper with 40 published news stories on the 2023 presidential election devoted 60% and 22.5% to 1 deck and double deck, respectively. *ThisDay* newspaper with 48% 1 deck/72 points and 26% apiece for double deck/36-72 and 2-36 points framed the 2023 presidential election news stories on the front, inside back and centre spread with adequate prominence, while *Daily Trust* newspaper devoted 30% to 1 deck/72 points and 40% to double deck/36-72 points, a clear indication of playing down the 2023 presidential election news stories.

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Figure 2: Distribution of Direction of Stories Published by the four newspapers studied

The data from Figure 2 show the direction of stories on the 2023 presidential election published by *The Nation*, *Daily Sun*, *ThisDay* and *Daily Trust* newspapers. Analysis shows that 42% of the stories (108) out of a total of 235 stories were favourable, and interestingly, *The Nation* newspaper contributed 41 favourable stories, *Daily Sun* 52, *ThisDay* newspaper 10, while the *Daily Trust* newspaper published 5 favourable stories.

The analysis further revealed that unfavourable direction was 40% (83 stories), while neutral stories attracted the least mean percent of 18 (44) stories, indicating a minimal level of objectivity in respect to the coverage of the 2023 presidential election by the four newspapers studied.

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Figure 3: Distribution of Favourable Direction According to Political Parties

Figure 3 displays the distribution of favourable stories according to political parties published by the four understudied newspapers, and available data indicates a total of 108 stories that were positively toned. Such information encouraged the electorates to support and vote for candidates and their various political parties, pointing out their achievements, competence and credibility. According to the data displayed in Figure 3, *The Nation* newspaper published 39 stories (95%) in favour of APC and its flag bearer, Ahmed Bola Tinubu, and despite the controversy that trailed his victory on February 25, 2023, *The Nation* was cautious in its choice of words in stories related to APC and its victorious candidate. *Daily Sun*, with a total number of 52 favourable stories, devoted 48 stories (92%) to APC, 1 story in favour of PDP and other political parties.

The analysis further revealed that *ThisDay* newspaper published 2 stories (20%) each in favour of APC, PDP and other parties, respectively, and 4 stories (40%) in favour of LP, whereas *Daily Trust* newspaper, with a total of 5 favourable stories, allocated 2

(40%) to PDP, 1 story (20%) to APC, NNPP and LP, respectively, and none (0%) to other parties.

From the available data, it is evident that *The Nation* and *Daily Sun* newspapers allocated 95% and 92% of their favourable stories to APC, while *ThisDay* and *Daily Trust* newspapers exhibited some level of objectivity and fair play by spreading their favourable stories across the political parties.

Figure 4: Distribution of Unfavourable Stories According to Political Parties

Figure 4 shows the distribution of unfavourable stories according to political parties by the four newspapers studied. Interestingly, the highest number of unfavourable stories were published against PDP 27 (32%), followed by APC 20 (24%), LP 18 (23.75%), NNPP 10 stories (12.75%) and other political parties 8 stories (8%).

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It is also manifest from data displayed on the above figure that *ThisDay* newspaper published the highest number of unfavourable stories, amounting to 33 stories, of which 15 stories (75%) were directed at APC, 10 unfavourable stories against PDP, 2 against NNPP, zero unfavourable stories against LP and 6 unfavourable stories against other political parties such as AD, SDP, and AC, among others. Considering the magnitude of the unfavourable stories, it is pertinent to clarify that the stories were analysed to cover the three phases of the scope of the study spanning the pre-election, the 2023 election and post-2023 election coverage, and shortly after the election where Ahmed Bola Tinubu emerged as the controversial winner, most unfavourable stories were directed at the APC. But the zoning principle, which did not favour the emergence of Atiku Abubakar, attracted more unfavourable publications against the PDP penultimate to the 2023 presidential election of February 25. For instance, on March 10, 2023, *The Nation* newspaper reported: Fayosa quits PDP, slams Atiku, Ayu for shunning Counsel.

Findings from Figure 4 also revealed the publication of 0% unfavourable stories by *The Nation* and *Daily Sun* newspapers against APC. Based on the distribution of unfavourable direction by the four studied newspapers, the reality of ownership influences partly and religious affiliations on direction have been amplified. *The Nation* newspaper is owned by Bola Ahmed Tinubu, the APC candidate and current President of Nigeria, while *Daily Sun* newspaper is owned by Orji Uzoh Kalu, a senator elected on the platform of the APC. This observation supports the submission of Ashameri & Udoakah (2021) that Nigerian newspapers have a tradition of being used as instruments of propaganda by politicians to further their ambitions and also support their parties and candidates.

Figure 5: Distribution of Neutral Stories According to Political Parties

Figure 5 shows the distribution of neutral stories according to political parties as published by the four understudied newspapers. From the displayed data, *The Nation* newspaper published 7 neutral stories out of a total of 44 stories which needed a definite position, especially objective reports on the 2023 presidential election, including tribunal cases that involved Bola Ahmed Tinubu and ANPP and LP, respectively. The analysis further revealed that *the Daily Sun* newspaper published the highest number of neutral stories, but the majority of the stories played down issues relating to the APC and their candidate in the 2023 presidential election. Accordingly, 12 stories (67%) were for APC, 2 stories (11%) for PDP and other parties, while 1 story (5.5%) was for NNPP and LP, respectively.

However, *ThisDay* newspaper, with a total of 16 neutral stories according to available data from Figure 5, published a fair spread of neutral stories: 3 stories

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(18.75%) for APC and PDP, 4 stories (25%) apiece for LP and other parties and 2 stories (12.5%) for NNPP.

Further revelation from data displayed in Figure 5 indicated *Daily Trust* newspaper with the least number of neutral stories (3 stories), 0% for APC and NNPP, while 1 story (33.3%) went for PDP, LP and other parties, respectively.

Discussion of findings

Research Question 1

How did the framing of election coverage vary across the four newspapers?

Figure 1 provides answers to the above research question. *The Nation*, *Daily Sun*, *ThisDay* and *Daily Trust* newspapers deliberately used 1 deck/72 point headlines on strategic pages of prominence to frame news stories on the 2023 presidential election. Apart from *the Daily Trust* newspaper, which used more double-deck/36-72 point headlines, the *Nation* newspaper contributed 21 leads (55.2%) of the 59 1-deck/72-point headlines; *Daily Sun*, 24 (60%); *ThisDay*, 11 (48%); and *the Daily Trust* newspaper, 3 (30%). When the 28.7% mean devoted to double-deck/36-72 points by the four understudied newspapers is added to the 48.3% 1-deck/72 points, a staggering 77% is the outcome. This clearly illustrates that the 2023 presidential election was strategically framed.

Furthermore, Figure 1 portrays the choice of words used in the leads of news stories on the 2023 presidential election. The use of such words as Muslim/Muslim ticket, terrorism sponsorship, “a rape on democracy”, Atiku vows to challenge Tinubu's election victory, certificate forgery, and Christian and Muslim candidates were used to frame issues revolving around the 2023 presidential election. By so doing, the studied newspapers adopted two news frames, which include game frame and issues framing. This practice aligns with an earlier finding by Obukodata & Enam (2016) that current and emerging issues could be strategically framed or presented in news stories depending on how they were deliberated by journalists or editorial boards for specific impact on the psyches of the audience members.

In a previous study, Muniz, Saldierna & Mararion (2018) submitted that game frame strategy is a game where politics and electoral process are presented separately as a set of interactive and related messages but spatially bound together, with the ultimate goal of winning an election. The four newspapers conspicuously amplified the electoral

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process and the candidates of 2023 presidential election separately but spatially bound together in their news coverage.

News stories in sharp contrast to features and editorials is expected to be a factual and objective account of events by the mass media, and the event or occurrence does not merit the status of news until it is reported by the mass media in a timely, balanced, objective and unbiased manner. But when it is given a perspective by the journalists and their editors, objectivity gives way to framing. According to McNemanim *et al.* (2021), media framing takes several dimensions, including but not restricted to the proportion of space, the ratio of soft to hard news, episodic stories versus general thematic frames and, of course, the tone of the news as well as the distribution of the stories among the political parties and candidates. Lending credence to this scholarly submission, Arowolo (2017) posits that newspaper framing is guided by the principle that rhetorical devices can be used in a strategic arrangement to convince audience members of the salience of a given position even as framing is a second layer of agenda setting. Thus, by placing most of the related headlines on the 2023 presidential election and also slanting the words in their leads, *The Nation*, *Daily Sun*, *ThisDay* and *Daily Trust* newspapers gave the audience members aspects of issues to think about and left them to form their perception based on how they could relate their understanding with other information they could access (Obukadata & Enam, 2016).

Research Question 2

Were there notable differences in the direction of coverage of the 2023 presidential election by the four newspapers?

A composite picture of the direction of stories on the coverage of the 2023 presidential election as they related to the various political parties is presented in Figures 3, 4 and 5; meanwhile, Figure 2 had earlier presented the distribution of stories generally without relating to political parties, and out of a total of 235 stories, 128 stories (42%) were favourable, 83 stories (40%) were unfavourable, and 44 stories (18%) were found to be neutral.

However, in a matter of specificity, Figure 3 isolated favourable stories and carefully analysed how *The Nation*, *Daily Sun*, *ThisDay* and *Daily Trust* newspapers toned their stories to favour the four prominent parties, including APC, PDP, NNPP, LP and other parties, in their editorial contents on the 2023 presidential election. This

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favourable disposition, especially on controversial issues that required a definite position, portrayed the correlation between ownership structure and party affiliation on the one hand and other intervening factors such as tribe and religion on objective and responsible journalism. According to the data displayed in Figure 4, *The Nation* newspaper published 39 stories (95%) in favour of APC and its flag bearer, Ahmed Bola Tinubu, ignoring the controversy that trailed his victory. Similarly, *the Daily Sun* newspaper devoted 48 favourable stories (92%) to the APC and 2% to the PDP, NNPP, LP and other parties, respectively, whereas the *ThisDay* and *Daily Trust* newspapers demonstrated some level of fairness by spreading their favourable stories across the political parties.

Figure 4 displayed unfavourable stories as they specifically related to the political parties, and *The Nation* newspaper published a total of 20 unfavourable stories on the 2023 presidential election, out of which 10 unfavourable stories (50%) were directed at PDP, especially the emergence of Alhaji Atiku, a northerner, as their presidential candidate; 7 (35%) unfavourable stories were directed against LP; 2 (10%) against NNPP; and 1 (5%) against other parties. *The Daily Sun* newspaper also had 20 unfavourable stories toned to an unfavourable direction (50%) against the Labour Party, 5 unfavourable stories (25%) against the PDP and NNPP, respectively, and 0% against the APC.

ThisDay and *Daily Trust* newspapers directed 45% and 50% of unfavourable stories against APC and 33% and 20% against PDP, while NNPP, LP and other parties were moderately castigated with unfavourable stories.

Going by the data displayed in Figure 5, a total of 44 neutral stories were recorded, and APC received 37%, PDP 19%, NNPP 8%, LP 19% and other parties had 7%. It is expected of journalists to be objective, unbiased and professional in news presentation, but the preponderance of positive stories by *The Nation* and *Daily Sun* newspapers in favour of APC and their presidential candidate in Figure 3 reinforces a previous submission by Ashameri & Udoakah (2021) that Nigerian newspapers are available tools of propaganda for paymaster politicians, which, of course, goes contrary to the ethics of journalism. It also goes against the tenets of professionalism when negative stories are levelled against the opposition, as witnessed from the analysis in Figure 3, where the same *Nation* and *Daily Sun* newspapers devoted 100% of unfavourable stories against other political parties and 0% against APC, whereas

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ThisDay newspaper with 33 unfavourable stories directed 75% (15 negative stories) against APC and 37% (10 negative stories), 20% (2 negative stories), and 18% (6 negative stories) against other political parties.

However, despite the disparity in the allocation of negative stories by the four newspapers on the coverage of the 2023 presidential election, they functioned in setting an agenda for topical discussion since the stories of a story is determined by the feeling the words and indeed the entire story is able to generate in the reader, and *The Nation*, *Daily Sun*, *ThisDay* and *Daily Trust* newspapers framed their stories using particular direction for specific effects (Valentine and Romentime, 2011; Asger Ali & Gill, 2022) based on their level of responsibility, involvement, blame and conflict.

In other words, the direction used by the four understudied newspapers during the coverage of the 2023 presidential election included positive, negative and neutral, which also revealed the underlying factors of ownership control, party affiliations, and economic influence, as well as religion and ethnic cleavages. That is not to say that the studied newspaper did not apply objectivity in their coverage of the 2023 presidential election, as obviated in Figure 4, where APC attracted 37%, PDP 19%, NNPP 8%, LP 19% and other parties 17%. It could be argued that APC enjoyed the power of incumbency and may have applied a subtle remote control mechanism, as supported by Salmon (2023), who recounted an ugly development which can be seen as anathema to the freedom and power of the press in Nigeria. The incident involved the Board of *ThisDay* Newspaper and Television claiming they had received two different requests to fire two of their reporters from high-ranking members of the ruling All Progressive Congress (APC).

Finally, the variation of direction by *The Nation*, *Daily Sun*, *ThisDay* and *Daily Trust* newspapers conforms with the scholarly explorations of Nwaboli and Ajibulu (2023) that newspapers, while reporting on politics, should use a blend of stories, not only attack or negative stories, to avoid shifting focus from the candidates and create antagonism between candidates and their supporters.

Research question 3

To what extent did the influence of ownership, party affiliation, and ethnicity differ among *The Nation*, the *Daily Sun*, *ThisDay*, and the *Daily Trust* newspapers?

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The answer to the above question is supplied in Figures 3, 4 and 5. The data in the three figures were generated from the content analysis which enabled the researcher to code words, themes and concepts within the published editorial content by *The Nation*, *Daily Sun*, *ThisDay*, and *Daily Trust* newspapers for the eventual analysis of the research (Wimmer & Dominic, 2020; Lou, 2023). The finding from Figure 4 indicates 55.5% of the stories were toned to favour the All Progressive Congress (APC) and their candidates, 15.5% favoured the PDP, 6% favoured the NNPP, and 15.5% favoured the LP, while 6.5% favoured other political parties.

A further breakdown of the analysis reveals that *The Nation* newspaper devoted 95% of published favourable stories to APC even after the 2023 presidential election and none to PDP, NNPP and LP. *The Daily Sun* newspaper, with a total of 52 stories, favoured 48 (92%) to APC and 2% to PDP, NNPP, LP and other parties comparatively. *ThisDay* newspaper with a total of 10 favourable stories devoted 40% to LP, 20% to PDP, APC and other parties but 0% to NNPP, whereas *Daily Trust* newspapers with 5 favourable stories devoted 40% to PDP, 20% to APC, NNPP and LP respectively and 0% to other parties.

Figure 4 displayed the distribution of unfavourable stories according to political parties, and from available data, the Peoples' Democratic Party (PDP) received the highest percentage (32%) of the total unfavourable stories, followed by the All Progressive Congress (APC) with 24%, the Labour Party with 23.75%, the New Nigerians Peoples Party (NNPP) with 12.75% and other political parties with 8%. However, a careful analysis revealed an almost similar trend to the findings from Figure 4, where *The Nation* and *Daily Sun* newspapers spared the APC unfavourable stories but rather unbundled such stories on other political parties, i.e., *The Nation* newspaper, PDP 50%, NNPP 10%, LP 35%, and other parties 5%. *Daily Sun*, PDP 25%, NNPP 25%, LP 50%, other parties 0%.

ThisDay and *Daily Trust* newspapers published more unfavourable stories against APC as follows: *ThisDay* newspaper: APC 45%, PDP 33%, NNPP 6%, LP 0% and other parties 18%. *Daily Trust* newspaper devoted 50% unfavourable stories to APC. 20% to PDP, 10% to NNPP, 10% to LP and 10% to other parties.

It is strongly believed that the media have the right to shape convictions by focusing on, explaining, and clarifying issues, events and people. Furthermore, agenda setting as a concept is not limited to the correspondence between the salience of a topic

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for the media and audience but also beams the searchlight on those who determine the setting of such an agenda (Uche, 1989; Folarin, 1998; Akakwandu, 2020).

Accordingly, fair play, truth and balance are the ingredients expected to spice up the credibility of the agenda-setting, thereby enhancing the salience of the topic. From the available data in Figures 4 and 5, it appears *The Nation* and *Daily Sun* newspapers exhibited favouritism toward APC in their direction in negation of fairness and balance, and this suggests the influence of ownership and party affiliation in the coverage of the 2023 presidential election. Comparatively, therefore, *ThisDay* and *Daily Trust* newspapers displayed disfavour to APC but moderately favoured PDP and other political parties. This is not strange considering the ownership structure of the four studied newspapers. *The Nation* newspaper is owned by Ahmed Bola Tinubu, the All Progressive Party presidential candidate who eventually emerged the winner of the 2023 election, while *Daily Sun* newspaper is owned by Orji Uzoh Kalu, a senator elected under the platform of APC from Abia State. *ThisDay* and *Daily Trust* newspapers, on the other hand, are owned by Nduka Obiaegbena and Media Trust Ltd, respectively, and both of them are professional journalists without established partisan affiliations.

This, of course, does not imply that the four newspapers totally negated objectivity in their coverage of the 2023 presidential election, as evidenced by the findings in Figure 5, which displayed the distribution of neutral stories. These were stories that required a definite position, but the understudied newspaper toed the path of professionalism and gave objective and balanced reports. A total of 44 neutral stories were published, out of which *The Nation* newspaper contributed 7, *Daily Sun* 18, *ThisDay* newspaper 16 and *Daily Trust* newspaper 3. The analysis further showed that *the Daily Sun* newspaper published the highest number of such objective and neutral stories, but the majority of the stories played down the post-election controversial issues, such as the tribunal proceeding and the inherent issues which were framed into the litigation. However, the findings from Figures 3, 4 and 5 clearly portray a divergence of opinion on the issue of ownership and party influence. But available data confirm the existence of glaring ownership and party affiliation influence since influence can best be measured through content analysis. There is a relationship between these findings and the earlier mentioned study. Thus Ashamameri & Udoakah (2021) in “A study of propaganda of newspaper ownership influence on political advertising in select Nigerian newspapers” confirmed that the data showed a great imbalance and obvious

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ownership influence in the use of propaganda elements, where the Punch newspaper published 40 (67.8%) advertisements containing propaganda elements in favour of the APC, while *The Nation* published 39 (92.3%) propaganda elements in favour of the APC.

Ashameri & Udoakah (2021) went further to reveal that most Nigerian newspapers are suspected to support certain candidates and parties during the process of election and that most of the newspapers are owned by the politicians. As earlier mentioned, ownership of the press and ownership coverage have been viewed as deliberate and conscious attempts to use the press in misleading or deceiving the public to attach importance and followership to the press owner for political gains.

Conclusion

This study comparatively analysed the framing of the Nigerian 2023 presidential election by four major newspapers: *The Nation*, *Daily Sun*, *ThisDay* and *Daily Trust*. The findings revealed that each newspaper adopted different framing techniques, influenced by their editorial policies, ownership structures, and ideological leanings.

The study identified dominant frames such as issue-based, personality-based, conflict and ethnic/religious frames. While some newspapers emphasised policy discussions and candidates' competencies, others focused on political controversies and ethnic and regional narratives as well as party affiliations. These variations in framing shaped public perceptions and influenced political discourse leading up to the election and beyond.

Furthermore, the comparative analysis highlighted how media bias played a role in shaping electoral narratives. Newspapers such as *The Nation* and *Daily Sun*, with close affiliations to certain political parties, tended to frame stories in ways that either promoted their preferred candidates or criticised opposition candidates. This is not to say that *ThisDay* and *Daily Trust* newspapers were totally free of such biases, but the publication of 95% and 92% favourable stories to APC by *The Nation* and *Daily Sun* newspapers, respectively, is a glaring testament to the negation of fair play and balance. Conversely, some newspapers maintained a more balanced approach, offering diverse perspectives on the election.

The study also underscores the role of newspapers in setting agendas for public discourse. The framing choices made by these newspapers did not only inform but also

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influenced voters' perceptions, reinforcing the media's role as a key player in the democratic process. However, the prevalence of sensationalism and ethnic-based narratives in some reports raises concerns about the media's responsibility in promoting national unity and informed decision-making.

In conclusion, the study demonstrates that newspapers played a significant role in shaping the narratives of the 2023 presidential election through the framing techniques. It calls for more responsible journalism, urging media outlets to prioritise issue-based reporting and factual analysis over partisan and sensational coverage. A free but responsible press is essential for strengthening democracy, fostering informed citizen participation, and ensuring electoral integrity in Nigeria.

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